

To Study The Perception Of The Postgraduate Students Of Assam University On The Changing Pattern Of Social Relationships In The Internet Age

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Abstract: Internet is one of the most amazing inventions of human civilization. The use of internet has increased dramatically in recent years among young adults. During the last decade, internet has largely influenced the social relationship pattern across the globe. A person can stay updated about the lives of friends and relatives all the time and can create stronger connections with the help of internet. But there is a flip side. Internet is changing our pattern of social interaction and relationships with each other. While internet allows us to connect with people with so much ease, it can also be detrimental to our traditional face-to-face social interactions and relationships. There is a big challenge to us as how to maintain a balance between the online and offline world. The present study aims to explore the perception of the postgraduate students of Assam University on the changing pattern of social relationships in the internet age. The study was conducted on 592 respondents from 16 departments of Assam University. The respondents perceived that there is a change in the pattern of social relationships in terms of both quality and quantity in the pre-internet and internet age. All the respondents were active users of internet. Depending on their daily internet usage in hours, they were categorized into light, moderate and heavy users. The data indicated that majority of the respondents were moderate users of internet. For most of the respondents, the preferred mode of social interaction is the traditional face-to-face mode. The preferred mode of social interaction for majority of the heavy internet users is the online mode while majority of the light and moderate users of internet preferred the in-person mode for social interaction.

INTRODUCTION:

Internet is one of the most amazing inventions of human civilization. The use of internet has increased dramatically in recent years among young adults. There has been a tremendous growth of internet use in India and worldwide in the last decade. Almost two-third of the world population has an internet connection today. As on 2022, China had more than one billion internet users, which is the highest amongst all the countries in the world, followed by India with more than 932 million internet users.

Internet World Stats (2015) in a survey reported that, there are more than 3 billion people in the world having Internet access. The growth of Internet usage has increased tremendously to 566.4% from year 2000 to 2012.

AT Kearney Global Research (2014) did a survey on internet use among Indians and reported that 53% of Indians are connected to the internet every waking hour which is higher than the global average of 51%.

Internet has become an integral part of our lives in the 21st century. As we open our eyes every morning, the first thing most of us do is to check our instant messaging applications and social networking applications for important messages and notifications. Same thing is done by most of us before closing our eyes at night. Thus, most of us start and end our day with internet only.

Internet has proved to be a boon for everyone especially during the recent pandemic period. With the onset of the COVID 19 pandemic, when the activities of the whole world came to a standstill, it is the internet that kept the ball rolling. Be it in the service sector, be it in the education sector, be it in the IT sector, be it in the medical sector and so on, internet played the role of a saviour and made the impossible things possible.

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE PRESENT STUDY

During the last decade, internet has largely influenced the social relationship pattern across the globe. People from distant places are coming together to form social groups online. These days, people are getting connected to each other across the globe with the help of the internet and the whole world is becoming a global village. Business has become easier and communication has become real time.

Social networking and instant messaging applications bring people together geographically and technology allows interactions to occur more frequently. Thus, a person can stay updated about the lives of friends and relatives all the time and can create stronger connections.

But there is a flip side. Internet is changing our pattern of social interaction and relationships with each other. These days many people prefer to stay connected with friends and families online rather than engaging with them in the traditional ways such as meeting face-to-face for a chat.

Thus, while internet allows us to connect with people with so much ease, it can also be detrimental to our traditional face-to-face social interactions and relationships as a whole. There is a big challenge to us as how to maintain a balance between the online and offline world.

As the number of internet users and the extent of internet use have been rapidly increasing during last few decades, researchers are trying to explore the influence of the use of internet on various behavioural aspects of the individuals.

Kraut et. al. (1998) in an article on “Internet Paradox: A social technology that reduces social involvement and psychological well- being” states that using the internet has many negative effects such as it lessens the face-to-face interaction between people. However, the author also states that communicating through social networks and the increased use of the internet builds relationships and self-esteem.

Brignall et. al. (2005) in an article on “The impact of internet communications on social interaction” states that the internet is a great tool but raises some great points of concern. The author states that the internet can negatively impact user’s privacy, impersonal communications, and cause isolation from others.

The present study aims to explore the perception of the postgraduate students of Assam University Silchar on the changing pattern of social relationships in the internet age.

Statement of the problem:

To study the perception of the postgraduate students of Assam University Silchar on the changing pattern of social relationships in the internet age.

Objective of the study

1. To find out the extent of internet use among the post graduate students of Assam University?
2. To examine the perception of the postgraduate students of Assam University on the changing pattern of social relationships in the internet age.
3. To find out the preferred mode of the post graduate students of Assam University for social interaction.
4. To explore the relationship between the extent of internet use of the post graduate students of Assam University and their preferred mode for social interaction.

Research Questions

1. What is the extent of internet use among the post graduate students of Assam University?
2. What is the perception of the postgraduate students of Assam University regarding the changing pattern of social relationship in the internet age?
3. What type of social interaction is preferred by the post graduate students of Assam University?
4. Is there any relationship between the extent of internet use of the post graduate students of Assam University and their preferred mode for social interaction?

DELIMITATION OF THE STUDY

Due to paucity of time at the disposal of the researcher, the study is restricted to the 2nd and 4th semester post graduate students of Assam University.

OPERATIONAL DEFINITIONS OF THE TERMS USED

Social Relationship:

A social relationship is any relationship between two or more individuals which involves social interaction. Social interaction forms the basis of social relationships.

With the evolution of digital civilization, a new type of relationship called 'Virtual relationship' has evolved with the use of e-mail, instant messaging, social networking which connects the whole world together with the help of the internet. It has been found from different studies that today's youth spend a lot of time in instant messaging and social networking applications like WhatsApp, Facebook, Instagram, Twitter etc. and the traditional social relationship patterns are changing rapidly.

In the present study, Social Relationship chiefly refers to the in-person social interaction on which the new age virtual interaction is making some impact. This study aims at examining the perception of the postgraduate students on social relationships in the internet age, and tries to find their preferences for social interaction.

Internet Age:

In the present study, Internet age refers to the time period since when the internet has become easily available for the use of general public across the nations. It is characterized by the new ways of accessing and sharing information, reducing the distances, incorporating new ways of communication etc.

Extent of Internet Use:

The internet is a global networking system that can be used on devices such as computer, laptop, smartphones etc. It has become an integral part of our life. There is almost no limit to what we can do using internet. The internet helps in real-time accessing and sharing of information, communicating with people across the globe, manage finances, online shopping, work from home, listen to our favourite music, watch videos, play games, and so on.

In this study, the extent of internet use refers to the time spent by the students in a day on internet in terms of hours.

Locale of the study

The study has been conducted at Assam University, Silchar (Latitude 24.68 degree North and Longitude 92.75 degree East) which is situated at Dargakona in the district of Cachar within the state of Assam. The university is situated at a distance 21 km from the district headquarter Silchar. The university is set amid sprawling hillocks, a typical landscape in the North East. The campus in an area of 600 acres surrounded by lakes and mountains provides an ideal environment for educational pursuit.

Drawing its 300 plus faculty from many disciplines, from all over the country, the university sustains a multidisciplinary approach to higher education.

Population:

The population of the present study is all the post graduate students of Assam University. The university has sixteen schools under which 40 departments are functioning at present. The current student strength is around 4600 out of which around 1500 are UG/IG students and around 650 are M Phil and Ph. D. research scholars. Thus, the total population of PG students is around 2500.

Sample and Sampling procedure

For the present study, the researcher has collected data from total 16 departments, (6 departments from Arts, 5 departments from Science, 1 department from Commerce and 4 departments from professional courses). The departments were selected purposively. The sample constituted of 592 postgraduate students studying in different departments of Assam University, Silchar.

Streamwise representation of samples

The stream wise representation is shown in the below table.

Table 1: Streamwise representation of samples

Stream	Sex		Total
	Male	Female	
Arts	70 (34.31%)	134 (65.69%)	N=204
Science	82 (42.71%)	110 (57.29%)	N=192
Commerce	25 (36.76%)	43 (63.24%)	N=68
Professional Courses	57 (44.53%)	71 (55.47%)	N=128
Total	N=234 (39.53%)	N=358 (60.47%)	N=592

Out of 592 respondents, 234(39.53%) were male and 358(60.47%) were female. Out of the 204 respondents from the Arts and Humanities departments, 70(34.31%) were male, and 134(65.69%) females. Out of the 192 respondents from science departments, 82(42.71%) were male and 110(57.29%) were female. Out of the 128 respondents from the departments offering professional courses, 57(44.53%) were male and 71(55.47%) were female. Out of the 68 respondents from the Commerce departments, 25(36.76%) were male and 43(63.24%) were female.

Tools used for the study

To realize the objectives of the present study, the following tools were developed by the researcher under the guidance of her supervisor.

- (i) A personal information schedule was developed by the researcher to assess the socioeconomic background of the respondents.
- (ii) To examine the extent of the use of the internet, a questionnaire has been developed by the researcher.
- (iii) A scale has been developed by the researcher to evaluate the perception of students regarding social relationships in the internet age.

Techniques of data analysis:

The data were described and analyzed with the help of percentage, mean value, and standard deviations for different categories of variables and inferences drawn accordingly.

Major Findings:

The major findings of the study in the context of the objectives and research questions are presented below.

Findings and conclusion on Objective 1, i.e., to find out the extent of internet use among the male and female post graduate students of Assam University.

(a) The findings on the Research Question of objective 1, i.e., “What is the extent of internet use among the postgraduate students of Assam University?”

To find out the extent of internet use among the postgraduate students of Assam University, the respondents were asked that how much time did they spend on internet every day.

TABLE 1: Sex wise distribution of the respondents and their daily internet usage

Daily Internet Use	Male N=234	Female N=358	Total N=592
Up to 1 hour	37 (15.81%)	72 (20.11%)	109 (18.41%)
1-2 hours	36 (15.38%)	51 (14.25%)	87 (14.69%)
2-3 hours	52 (22.22%)	70 (19.55%)	122 (20.61%)
3-4 hours	21 (8.97%)	43 (12.01%)	64 (10.82%)
4-5 hours	20 (8.55%)	40 (11.17%)	60 (10.14%)
5-6 hours	66 (28.21%)	81 (22.63%)	147 (24.83%)
Above 6 hours	02 (0.85%)	01 (0.28%)	03 (0.51%)
Total	N=234	N=358	N=592

The sample consisted of 592 respondents. The data indicated that each and every respondent was an active user of internet.

Out of 592, approximately 25% respondents spend five to six hours in a day on internet followed by 21% two to three hours, 18% up to one hour, 15% one to two hours, 11% three to four hours, 10% four to five hours and only 0.51% above 6 hours.

There are 358 female respondents. Amongst them, 22.63% respondents spend five to six hours on internet every day followed by 20.11% up to one hour, 19.55% two to three hours, 14.25% one to two hours, 12.01% three to four hours, 11.17% four to five hours and only 0.28% above six hours.

Out of 592 respondents, 234 were males. Amongst them, 28.21% respondents spend five to six hours on internet in a day, 22.22% two to three hours, 15.81% up to one hour, 15.38% one to two hours, 8.97% three to four hours, 8.55% four to five hours and only 0.85% above six hours.

The above data indicates that the male percentage is on the higher side when it comes to using internet for more than 5 hours daily in comparison to female while the female percentage is on the higher side when we compare the data with males using internet for a duration up to 1 hour in a day.

The males outnumbered females in the one to two hour and two to three hours usage category whereas the female outnumbered males in three to four hours and four to five hours usage of internet in a day.

Thus, there is some variation in the extent of internet use between the male and female population in terms of percentage.

The respondents were categorized according to their average daily internet usage time. Table 2 shows the sex wise representation of the category of the respondents as per their average daily internet use in hours.

Table 2: Sex wise distribution of the respondents’ daily internet usage

Internet use	SEX		Grand Total N=592
	Male	Female	
Light (Up to 2 hours per day)	73 (31.20%) N=234	123 (34.36%) N=358	196 (33.11%) N=592
Moderate (2-5 hours per day)	93 (39.74%) N=234	153 (42.74%) N=358	246 (41.56%) N=592
Heavy (More than 5 hours per day)	68 (29.06%) N=234	82 (22.91%) N=358	150 (25.34%) N=592
Total	N=234	N=358	N=592

The categorization was done by calculating the mean of the daily internet usage of all the respondents in hours. The mean came out to be 3.56 and the standard deviation 1.84. With the help of this mean and standard deviation, the researcher classified the respondents into three categories viz. Heavy users, Moderate users and Light users based on their daily internet usage.

In the present study, Heavy users refer to those who spend more than 5 hours on internet daily, Light users are those who spend up to 2 hours and Moderate users are those who spend three to five hours on internet every day.

Out of 592 respondents, 41.56% are moderate users of internet, followed by 33.11% light users and 25.33% heavy users. The data indicates that majority of the respondents are moderate users of internet.

Out of 234 male respondents, 39.74% are moderate users, 31.20% are light users and 29.06% are heavy users of internet.

From the above data, it is evident that the percentage of male respondents is on the higher side in the heavy user category while that of female respondents is on the higher side in the light and moderate user category.

Thus, we can say that males outnumbered females in the heavy user category in terms of percentage whereas the females outnumbered males in the light and moderate users category.

Findings on Objective 2, i.e., to examine the perception of the postgraduate students of Assam University on the changing pattern of social relationships in the internet-age.

Findings on Research Question of Objective 2, i.e., what is the perception of the post graduate students on social relationship in the internet age?

To fulfil this objective, the respondents were presented with 8 items to which they were instructed to respond by choosing from three options viz. Agree, Disagree and Not Sure.

Table 3 shows the sex wise representation of responses on the items related to the perception of respondents on the changing pattern of social relationships in the internet age.

Table 3: Sex wise representation of responses on the items related to the perception of respondents on the changing pattern of Social Relationship in the internet age

Items	Agree			Disagree			Not sure			Grand Total
Item No	Male	Female	Total	Male	Female	Total	Male	Female	Total	
1	128 (54.70%) N=234	191 (53.35%) N=358	319 (53.89%) N=592	52 (22.22%) N=234	84 (23.46%) N=358	136 (22.47%) N=592	54 (23.08%) N=234	83 (23.18%) N=358	137 (23.14%) N=592	592
2	229 (97.86%) N=234	297 (82.96%) N=358	526 (88.85%) N=592	05 (2.14%) N=234	61 (17.04%) N=358	66 (11.15%) N=592	-	-	-	592
3	225 (96.15%) N=234	319 (89.11%) N=358	544 (91.89%) N=592	02 (0.85%) N=234	23 (6.42%) N=358	25 (4.22%) N=592	07 (2.99%) N=234	16 (4.47%) N=358	23 (3.89%) N=592	592
4	212 (90.60%) N=234	314 (87.71%) N=358	526 (88.85%) N=592	19 (8.12%) N=234	22 (6.15%) N=358	41 (6.93%) N=592	03 (1.28%) N=234	22 (6.15%) N=358	25 (4.22%) N=592	592
5	213 (91.03%) N=234	325 (90.78%) N=358	538 (90.88%) N=592	16 (6.84%) N=234	23 (6.42%) N=358	39 (6.59%) N=592	05 (2.14%) N=234	10 (2.79%) N=358	15 (2.53%) N=592	592
6	225 (96.15%) N=234	332 (92.73%) N=358	557 (94.09%) N=592	06 (2.56%) N=234	23 (6.42%) N=358	29 (4.90%) N=592	03 (1.28%) N=234	03 (0.83%) N=358	06 (1.01%) N=592	592
7	45 (19.23%) N=234	50 (13.97%) N=358	95 (16.05%) N=592	138 (58.97%) N=234	215 (60.05%) N=358	353 (59.63%) N=592	51 (21.79%) N=234	93 (25.98%) N=358	144 (24.32%) N=592	592
8	59 (25.21%) N=234	95 (26.54%) N=358	154 (26.01%) N=592	71 (30.34%) N=234	136 (37.99%) N=358	207 (34.97%) N=592	104 (44.44%) N=234	127 (35.47%) N=358	231 (39.82%) N=592	592

Item no. 1: Social relations are flourishing in the internet-age.

Out of 592 respondents, 53.92% agreed to this item, followed by 23.14% not sure and 22.47% disagreed.

Thus, more than 50% of the respondents perceives that social relationships are flourishing in the internet age and the remaining respondents are either not sure or disagree to this item.

Item no. 2. There is a variation (in terms of quality and quantity) in social relationships in the pre-internet and internet age.

Out of 592, 88.85% agreed to this item and 11.15% disagreed and no one is unsure of this item.

A vast majority of the respondents perceives that there is a variation in social relationships in terms of both quality and quantity in the pre-internet and internet age, i.e., before and after the evolution of internet in human civilization.

Item no. 3. We are socially related to a greater number of people in the internet age than in the pre-internet age.

Amongst the 592 respondents, approximately 92% agreed to this item, 4% disagreed and 4% not sure.

Thus, majority of the respondents perceives that we are socially related to a greater number of people in the internet age than in the pre-internet age.

Item no. 4. In the internet age, we are more connected to people residing in distant places than to those living nearby.

88.85% of the total respondents agreed to this item while 6.93% disagreed and 4.22% were not sure.

Thus, majority of the respondents perceives that with the evolution of internet, we have become more connected to the people residing in distant places than to those living nearby.

Item no. 5. In the internet age, we are more informed about the lives of our long-distance friends on social media than our family and friends living nearby.

Out of 592, approximately 91% agreed to this item, 6.59% disagreed and 2.53% were not sure.

Thus, a vast majority of the respondents are of the opinion that we are more informed about what is happening in the lives of our long-distance friends on social media than our family and friends living nearby.

Item no. 6. Use of internet reduces face to face communication.

Approximately 94% of the total respondents agreed to this item while 5% disagreed and 1% not sure.

Thus, a clear majority of the respondents believed that use of internet could reduce the face-to-face interaction between people.

Item no. 7. Online relationships are as stable as our in-person relationships.

Amongst 592 respondents, 59.63% disagreed to this item, followed by 24.32% not sure and 16.05% disagreed.

Almost 60% of the respondents perceives that online relationships are not as stable as our in-person relationships.

Thus, the postgraduate students of Assam University gave more value to in-person relationships than virtual or online relationships.

Item no. 8. Internet helps relationships last over time and space.

Out of 592, 39.82% were not sure, while 34.97% disagreed and 26.01% agreed to this item.

Thus, majority of the respondents were either not sure or disagreed on this item. And only about 26% of the respondents perceive that internet helps relationships last over time and space,

The data depicts that though the respondents acknowledge the fact that there has been more ease in connecting with people socially in the internet age in terms of quantity yet they believe that online relationships cannot be as stable as our in-person relationships and there is some doubt about the durability of online relationships in the long run. Also, too much reliance on internet and social media to connect with people is making us less aware about the whereabouts of the people living nearby.

Findings on Objective 3, i.e., to find out the preferred mode of social interaction of the post graduate students of Assam University?

Findings on Research Question of Objective 3, i.e., What type of social interaction is preferred by the post graduate students of Assam University?

To fulfil this objective, the following item was presented to the respondents to which they were instructed to respond by choosing from three options viz. Agree, Disagree and Not Sure.

Description of Item No 1. I prefer to interact with people using Facebook, WhatsApp, Instagram, and similar social media applications than to interact with them in person.

TABLE 4: Sex wise representation of respondents’ preferred mode of social interaction

Items	Agree			Disagree			Not sure		
	Male	Female	Total	Male	Female	Total	Male	Female	Total
1	78 (33.33%) N=234	112 (31.28%) N=358	190 (32.10%) N=592	133 (56.84%) N=234	204 (56.98%) N=358	337 (56.92%) N=592	23 (9.83%) N=234	42 (11.73%) N=358	65 (10.98%) N=592

Table 4 shows the sex wise representation of the preferred mode of social interaction of the respondents. Out of 592 respondents, 56.92% disagreed to this item, followed by 32.09% agreed and 10.98% not sure. Approximately 57% of the respondents prefer to interact with people in-person.

Thus, most of the respondents preferred the traditional face to face mode for social interaction to the online mode.

Findings on Objective 4, i.e., to explore the relationship between the extent of internet use of the post graduate students of Assam University and their preferred mode of social interaction.

Findings on Research Question of Objective 4, i.e., is there any relation between the extent of internet use of the postgraduate students of Assam University and their preferred mode of social interaction?

To find out the relation between the extent of internet use of the postgraduate students of Assam University and their preferred mode of social interaction, a cross-table has been prepared. Table 5 shows the sex wise distribution of respondents as per their internet use category and the preferred mode for social interaction as per item no.1 of objective 3.

TABLE 5: Sex wise distribution of the internet use category of respondents and their preferred mode of social interaction as per item no. 1 of objective 3

Internet Use	Agree			Disagree			Not Sure		
	Male	Female	Total	Male	Female	Total	Male	Female	Total
Heavy	29 (37.18%) N=78	38 (33.93%) N=112	67 (35.26%) N=190	30 (22.56%) N=133	33 (16.18%) N=204	63 (18.69%) N=337	09 (39.13%) N=23	11 (26.19%) N=42	20 (30.77%) N=65
Moderate	32 (41.02%) N=78	49 (43.75%) N=112	81 (42.63%) N=190	53 (39.85%) N=133	93 (45.59%) N=204	146 (43.32%) N=337	08 (34.78%) N=23	11 (26.19%) N=42	19 (29.23%) N=65
Light	17 (21.79%) N=78	25 (22.32%) N=112	42 (22.11%) N=190	50 (37.59%) N=133	78 (38.23%) N=204	128 (37.98%) N=337	06 (26.09%) N=23	20 (47.62%) N=42	26 (40.00%) N=65

190 respondents agreed to the item no. 1 of objective 3. Amongst them, 42.63% are moderate users of internet, followed by 35.26% heavy users and 22.11% light users.

Out of the 337 respondents who disagreed with the item, 43.32% are moderate users, 37.98% light users and 18.69% heavy users.

The data also reflects that out of the 150 heavy users, 44.67% agreed to the item and 42.00% disagreed, while 13.33% are not sure.

Amongst 246 moderate users, 59.35% disagreed, 32.93% agreed and 7.72% are not sure.

Out of the 196 light users, 65.31% disagreed, followed by 21.43% agreed and 13.26% not sure.

Thus, the preferred mode of social interaction for majority of the heavy users is the online mode while majority of the light and moderate users preferred the in-person or traditional face to face mode for social interaction.

Conclusion:

From the present study, we can conclude that majority of the post graduate students of Assam University fall under the category of moderate users of internet. Approximately one third of the respondents belong to the light user category and approximately one fourth belong to the heavy user category. Males outnumbered females in the heavy user category and the vice-versa in the light and moderate user category.

The respondents perceived that there is a change in the pattern of social relationships in terms of both quality and quantity in the pre-internet and internet age.

For majority of the respondents, the preferred mode of social interaction is the traditional in-person mode over the online mode.

The preferred mode of social interaction for majority of the heavy users is the online mode while majority of the light and moderate users preferred the in-person mode for social interaction.

Thus, the extent of internet use seems to have some influence in the selection of the preferred mode of social interaction by the respondents.

Suggestions for further research:

- a. The present study is limited to the 16 departments of Assam University, Silchar campus. This study could be replicated using a representative sample from all the 40 departments of Assam University.
- b. The study can be replicated using a representative sample from all the universities of the state of Assam.
- c. This study was limited to the post graduate students of Assam University. It can be further extended to the UG/IG students of Assam University.
- d. The study can be replicated in other universities, colleges, and schools in the regional, national and international level.

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